

Article

Designing an EAL Syllabus for Young Learners in a Bilingual or International School

Yanwei Sun

Hangzhou Yungu School, China

Abstract

Following the rise of bilingual international schools in China, many learners of primary school age face huge barriers to academic success at school due to weaknesses in language proficiency. In my experience, without sufficient language support, not only is the academic growth of many young learners impeded, their social life and even their mental health suffer. This study investigates how an understanding of course design for primary learners will help prepare English language courses that support an effective transition to a bilingual school environment. Cognitive factors, physical factors, and the environment are discussed and serve as lenses through which methodologies, including needs analysis, syllabus framework, and assessments are reviewed and conducted. The overall design is considered to have reached the original goals and have fulfilled learners' needs with evidential assessments and stakeholders' consensus.

Keywords

EAL for young learners, course design, cognitive factors

1 Introduction

This research is conducted as there is a growing trend of sending primary school students to schools where English is the dominant instructional language. The accompanying challenges primarily reside on three levels: language barriers, learning experience with other subjects taught in English, and social-emotional needs, like socialising and making general inquiries. This particular young group (aged 6-10) is viewed at their optimal learning stage in widely accepted theories; an emphasised notion among the arguments is that younger learners learn in a “more natural” way ([Gardner & Lambert, 1972](#)). However, the danger of a belief in “natural learning” will not only miss out this most effective teaching period; a series of problems could also occur due to a lack of constructive intervention. This article explores the variables in real teaching scenarios that could help young learners improve language proficiency and academic readiness. This study mainly focuses on three learners who have just joined a British school in the UK. The assessment and findings are qualitatively gathered and analysed.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Cognitive factors

There is a vast amount of literature devoted to explaining how primary learners learn. Defined as concrete operators, 6-11-year-olds cross a threshold between egocentric thinking, to more logical and abstract thought (Piaget & Inhelder, 1969). The implication is that courses can begin to incorporate activities based on abstract and logical thinking. Activities based on sorting, categorising, and building on prior knowledge can be used effectively by course designers (Read, 2008). To make the most of their natural learning characteristics, I integrate approaches like task-based learning (Willis & Willis, 2007) and games, play, competition, and creative tasks into courses (Harley, 1994). Piaget also stressed the importance of children actively constructing meaning through active participation and experience. According to Vygotsky (1997), significant development takes place when students collaborate with more capable adults or peers. This “significant other” can extend learners’ cognitive development. For course designers, incorporating scaffolding activities such as modelling, questioning, and supportive teacher talk can push students into the zone of proximal development. Some argue that form and linguistic knowledge should not be prioritised due to young learners’ (YLS) still-developing cognitive ability and lack of systematic understanding. However, through story and parable reading, fun tasks and purposeful activities (Breen & Candlin, 1980; Cameron, 2001), I have found that learners can retain and use the target language through noticing and repeating lexical or grammatical patterns through songs, chants, and stories.

The context of learning is crucial for YLS as they are still developing abstract thinking skills (Lightbown & Spada, 1999). Familiar contexts offer opportunities for personalisation, and vocabulary memorisation (Nagy et al., 1985). Therefore, selected topics and materials should be interesting and relevant (Graves, 1996), and include both imaginative and creative thinking and also familiar personalised topics. Additionally, as Yalden (1987) suggests, the context of learning should demonstrate some degree of continuity, through which YLS could extend and explore understanding and practice of existing knowledge based on themes or topics. Project work can develop the understanding of language and world knowledge in a meaningful, memorable, and student-centred way, suggesting topic based syllabuses are effective.

2.2 Physical factors

Another characteristic of this age group is that young learners have high levels of energy and feel eager to engage non-verbally during learning (Lightbown & Spada, 1999). This suggests that activities should incorporate total physical response, which includes role-play and kinaesthetic activities. The importance of high energy activities must also be accompanied by balancing them with quieter, calmer, and reflective activities (Halliwell, 1992) to manage energy levels and maximise focus. YLS also display difficulties regarding motor skills required for effective learning. For example, YLS’ writing and transcription ability do not keep up with their speaking skills in the early stages of learning due to their constrained physical development and limited concentration. Written production, sometimes, does not play a leading role in diagnosing a YL’s communication proficiency.

2.2.1 Immersion

Another important factor is the importance of immersion teaching is another important factor (Cameron, 2001). Children can learn language more naturally than adults, which suggests an emphasis on exposure to target language, meaningful communication, and pattern identification, rather than explicit grammar teaching (Johnson & Swain, 1997). Storytelling, role plays, the use of audio-visual material and authentic communicative tasks can emphasise natural acquisition over formal learning found in an adult classroom. A complete avoidance of L1 may seem difficult with YLS, especially beginners, but my experience has

suggested that, although there may be times when L1 seems more efficient, extremely judicious use of L1 should be considered to develop a “sense of self” which is unique to the second language (Hasslegreen & Caudwell, 2016). Teachers can create an “artificial” English-speaking environment through classroom decoration and instructional language. This can be complemented by appropriate homework which encourages natural exposure to L2 at home, such as cartoon episodes on TV played by parents, who should also be considered as key stakeholders in the course design process.

2.2.2 Implications

Given the aforementioned cognitive factor, a meaning-focused course based on intrinsically motivating tasks, purposeful activities, creative tasks and games is necessary. It is worth noting that scaffolding activities to push learners into the zone of proximal development, materials and topics based on learners’ interests to facilitate contextualisation and personalisation are absolutely essential. For the ease of connectedness and relevance to the content, continuity of context and concrete topics should be embedded and ought to be adjusted considering learners’ cognitive, motor and linguistic skills.

To fulfil the physical movement need, peer collaboration and peer support can be a key element to diversify the interactive mode, as well as other stirrers and settlers to vary pace and keep focus. Lastly, I will set routines for class and out-of-class activities. Parents are included to support the latter activities to co-develop an immersive L2 environment by playing authentic English materials at home.

3 Methodology

This study is primarily led by me and supported by three students’ homeroom teachers, subject teachers, and parents. I collected first and second hand information from interviews conducted with them, classroom observations and homework analysis against rubrics. As for the school, initiated by the primary school head and homeroom teachers, this project is also undertaken as action research, noted by Ferrance (2000), “action research is a collaborative activity among colleagues searching for solutions to every day, real problems experienced in schools, or looking for ways to improve instruction and increase student achievement” (p. 1). With qualitative research being the leading method in investigating, quantitative analysis as supplementary is designed for data collection and projection, as well as comparison.

3.1 Participants

The group consists of three learners who have transferred this term to an independent school in Leeds, UK. EAL lessons are scheduled on Friday afternoons to assist their transitional period. They all need to improve their English to a sufficient level to be able to understand lessons, participate in varied school activities independently, make friends, and enjoy school life. They are respectively Xavier (aged 7), Olivia (aged 8), and Monica (aged 9), and English is their second or third language.

3.2 Investigation before course designing

According to Nunan (1988), objective needs is a collection of factual information, such as age, nationality, home language, and linguistic level. Subjective needs are the perceptions of the learner about learning, the content and approaches preferred and their perceived current language competence. Since the primary aim of this course is to build learners’ current language proficiency to a level where they can participate in school, we must also consider the target situation (Richards, 2001). This comparison between current and target situations is known as a gap analysis (Graves, 1996; Richards, 2001).

3.3 Instructions

I used observations, questionnaires, and interviews to collect information. Firstly, by observing learners' in-class and after-class behaviours and performances, I gained a holistic view of their English ability within a "normal" context. I noted their prior knowledge, learning habits, difficulties in understanding, as well as strengths seen in observations (see Appendix B). I also interviewed the students using L1 to understand their personal and educational background, struggles, worries, and motivations in more detail. I used L1 in the interviews to promote rapport and trust (Richards, 2001). In addition, a questionnaire was given to teachers regarding the areas that students struggle with in class.

This triangulation between observations, interviews with teachers, and interviews with students helped me build a holistic picture of both objective and subjective needs. During the course, it is of equal importance to conduct ongoing needs analysis based on learning progress, to ensure that lessons address learners' needs. Emergent needs are to be recorded in a class journal with individual learners' key performance progress and needs.

3.4 Diagnostic testing

The approach of the diagnostic testing is meant to discover their function capabilities in a real-class setting; therefore, the test itself is highly dynamic with regards to the interaction part and the testing formats. This idea is harvested from Blatchford's (1971) view that when calculating the sum of several parts, your discoveries should be more than a number itself, rather, a holistic picture of this learner's proficiency in their learning context.

3.4.1 Instrument

The diagnostic test methods used were speaking, reading and listening comprehension. One consideration is these skills were identified as particular weaknesses from the homeroom teachers and specified by the learners themselves as problem areas. Another is that writing is not tested at this stage due to their teachers' suggestion of prioritising spoken production. Moreover, writing is not explicitly required as a learning goal for the regular class, either.

For reading skills, I used the Oxford Reading Tree as my main testing materials, along with comprehension questions provided. The Oxford Reading Tree is the dominant reading material in this primary school, so results can usefully locate the learners' English levels in comparison with their peers. The test started from Band 1. I used this because homeroom teachers specified that the Oxford Tree was best aligned with in-class activities based on building enjoyment in independent reading and developing literacy skills. The level of reading materials was gradually increased according to performance and learners proceeded to the next band if they answered the questions correctly.

3.4.2 Testing materials

For listening and speaking, I designed a series of activities which reflected classroom demands that replicated classroom scenarios that I had observed students struggling with, and also areas which their homeroom teachers specified as difficulties in classroom performance. Activities included comprehending and following instructions, conversation on daily topics, making contributions in class and answering questions based on lesson content, asking for clarification, requesting help, and initiating conversations.

4 Findings

Overall, it was clear that diagnostic testing revealed key areas of concern which corresponded to the

previous needs analysis. They included difficulty in reading comprehension due to deficiencies in vocabulary and grammar knowledge, hesitancy and limitations in speaking ability, a lack of classroom language to compensate for language deficiencies, difficulty following the main ideas in written and listening texts, and difficulty understanding and responding to questions from the teacher and peers.

4.1 Needs analysis

The key themes which emerged from my initial needs analysis were that the learners struggled with everyday classroom interaction and were unable to participate as well as native English-speaking students in plenary and group tasks. They lacked basic language for turn-taking, giving opinions, and asking for clarification. Interviews revealed that they often felt lost during plenary phases. They felt very motivated to participate but felt that they were “being judged for poor English” and grammar mistakes. They also lacked vocabulary related to the topics. They found reading especially difficult and had a slow reading pace which hindered their ability to participate. They also said they did not seek help if they were struggling and became withdrawn if they were unclear on task instructions or activities.

4.1.1 Priorities emerging from the needs analysis and the diagnostic testing

The following learning priorities are intended to equip learners with essential skills and knowledge of the language (Linse, 1993) to navigate and function in this brand new, even intimidating, L2-speaking community:

Spoken production (SP)

1. Constructing meanings more accurately and confidently
2. Asking for clarification and information
3. More confidence in seeking help verbally from peers and teachers

Listening (L)

4. Familiarise with general conversation topics within a school context
5. Comprehend and follow instructional language
6. Identify the main idea in a conversation
7. familiarise with a wide range of questions they could be asked in a class

Reading (R)

8. Improve reading skills for general understanding and detail
9. Develop an interest in pleasure reading
10. Enlarge vocabulary and grammar base
11. Recount and discuss a story after reading

5 Curriculum

The findings reveal that the immediate growth would benefit the learners are spoken production, listening, and reading. The following discussion expands on approaches for teaching which revolves around these three areas.

5.1 Teaching principles

There are many different approaches to syllabus design which can inform content, scope, and sequencing of courses (Graves, 1996). The approaches I have selected are broadly a functional-notional syllabus with

a strong focus on task-based learning. Functional-notional is an approach that organises teaching materials based on the notions and ideas that are essential for communication needs in certain situations (Finocchiaro & Brumfit, 1993). Focusing on functional phrases will help build fluency, accuracy, and confidence in the key areas identified in section 2, such as asking for clarification, initiating turns, and giving opinions.

Task-based learning, as mentioned above, promotes attention to meaning, purpose, and negotiation (Candlin, 1987), which would naturally prioritise constructing meanings and reduce learners' concern about being grammatically correct. Since the learners' primary need is to be able to participate actively in class, school events, and activities with basic language, it is thus vital for me to bear in mind the potential challenges and situations they struggle with.

Another key influence is a topic-based syllabus which helps build understanding of common topics identified by teachers and students in the needs analysis as common classroom topic areas.

5.2 Teaching objectives

The goals of a course are statements that describe the general purposes of a course and the objectives are statements about how the goals will be achieved (Graves, 2000, pp. 75-76). When it comes to differences, Brown (1995) points out that it is their level of specificity, and that objectives should be measurable and observable. The goals of this course are to help students gain basic linguistic knowledge and communicative skills for purposes of socialising, participating in school activities, and achieving better performance (See Appendix A). In order to do this, I have identified the following objectives:

Spoken production (SP)

1. Learners can share their thoughts and opinions in a simple structured manner with an audible voice in class/group discussions
2. Learners can ask for clarification or new information when they need to
3. Learners can request for help and initiate conversation with peers
4. Learners can engage in general conversation topics within a school context with appropriate amount of contribution

Listening (L)

5. Learners can follow basic instructional language without support
6. Learner can identify the main idea in a conversation/text and respond
7. Learners can comprehend common classroom questions easily or infer them within the context

Reading (R)

8. Learners' reading comprehension improves
9. Learners enjoy reading more and show willingness to share ideas and insights from stories
10. Learners expand vocabulary and grammatical structures

5.3 Teaching methods

To comply with the findings in section 3, the main approach of teaching adopted is task-based. Considered as a communication-oriented approach, its primary focus on meaning – making can boost learners' confidence and help achieve their attitude goals. In activities, YLs enjoy games, roles, and completion which might successfully divert their attention from concerns for accuracy as a result. Also, for YLs whose energy levels are high, engaging in activities and tasks are practically meaningful and beneficial for their full engagement. Furthermore, a series of tasks are based on life scenarios, which are crucial for their readiness in real-time communication. Since it has been discussed that storytelling plays

a leading role in literacy, this approach is going to be implemented as a routine activity. Moreover, to execute the implication about routines and attitudes in learning, a reading routine can be viewed as fairly effective in building learners' routines and attitudes (Ellis & Brewster, 2002; Martinez, 2007).

5.4 Teaching materials

I followed two leading principles when selecting materials: a high level of relevance and authenticity in relation to the school context, and the level of engagement. Since the EAL sessions take place on Friday afternoons, when the children feel tired and are excited about the weekend, I want them to feel these sessions are interesting enough for them to look forward to. In terms of materials, I want to diversify and enliven the materials by using animation clips, pictures, and toys to stimulate their learning interests. Based on the diagnostic test, I notice that they all very much enjoy listening to and watching electronic books. Also, I will use subject materials and worksheets from teachers and adapt them accordingly. I will assign appropriate amounts and types of homework to assist continuity of learning.

6 Assessment

6.1 Principles of assessment

When designing an assessment format for the three learners, I realise that the predominant principle is testing what has been taught, which is considered the cardinal rule of assessment (Graves, 2000). In this course, to make the test process as minimally invasive as possible, both formative and summative assessments are conducted. The major difference (Hughes, 1989) between these two assessments is that formative assessment focuses on the progress, so the immediate adjustments in teaching can be made. Summative assessment, usually conducted at the end of a year or a term, measures what has been achieved by learners. Furthermore, as Graves (2000) describes, "Needs assessment is linked to both assessments of learning and course evaluation" (p. 209). It is thus necessary to ensure that needs analysis, course design, and assessment are constructively aligned with regards to the objectives and the content tested. This also fulfils the requirement for validity, which is a criterion that measures how far the test assesses what it claims to (Gipps, 1994).

Table 1

Course Assessment Plan – Learning Outcomes

Learning Objective (SP, L, Formative (F) Assessment R).	Summative (S) Assessment (see Appendix 6)
SP1	Directly observe and evaluate class performance (F2, S4 S3, S4 in tables 2 and 3) and work produced (F3, S2) instead of asking them to have a simulated conversation with me
SP2	F1; F2 S1, S3, S4
SP3	F1; F2 S4
SP4	F; F2 S3, S4
L1	F1; F2 S4, S5
L2	F3 S3
L3	F1; F4 S1, S2, S4
R1	F3 S3
R2	F2; F4 S3, S4
R3	F1 F4 S1, S2, S3, S4

Table 2

Course Assessment Plan-Layout

Assessment type	Format	Frequency/Time of Conduction	Materials
Formative (F)	F1: In-class observation	Multiple times/lesson	Class content
	F2: Mainstream lesson observation	Twice/month	Class work/task
	F3: Homework examination	Once/week	Homework
	F4: Interview with teachers	Twice/month	Teaching journal
Summative (S)	S1: Interview with students	Once/month	Teaching journal
	S2: Role-play tests	The final week of the course	Self-invented or adapted tasks
	S3: Reading comprehension test	One day at the school during the last week of the term	Teaching journal and comments
	S4: Interview with teachers	The final week of the course	Teaching journal
	S5: School time observation	One day at the school during the last week of the term	Observation notes

Secondly, it is vital to adhere to the principle of “learner-centred testing” since the primary purpose of assessment is to serve the students. By assessing their achievement and progress, further teaching plans can be developed (Bailey, 1997). Assessment criteria should be personalised and criterion-referenced (Cameron, 2001). In this case, Monica’s reading level should progress to Level 4 and Xavier’s and Olivia’s arrive at Level 3. Further, learners should be clearly informed about the criteria. Hence, at the beginning of the course and during the monthly interview (S1) with students, I would let them know where they are, where they could be and how to get there. However, I would not consider self-assessment (Cameron, 2001) as an effective tool as, due to their overall language proficiency and developing cognitive ability, they might not grasp the criteria fully enough to make fair judgements.

Thirdly, from a development-oriented perspective, I agree with Weir and Roberts (1995) that the assessment process should involve all the stakeholders. I want to take account of their homeroom teachers’ continuous feedback, given that they gain first-hand knowledge of learners’ performance and improvement on a daily basis. Moreover, compared to my 2-hour lesson per week, their homeroom teachers can draw on a more significant amount of time to provide evidential details and holistic assessment.

Lastly, in contrast to the conventional pencil-and-paper test, I believe the assessment should reflect students’ real communicative skills and abilities needed when engaging in school activities and classroom tasks, as well as socialisation, as discussed in sections 1 and 2. As Graves (2000) observes, “if you are teaching a speaking and listening course whose objectives include being able to speak in ‘real world’ situations, then your assessment plan will include ways to assess students’ ability to speak in those situations” (p. 211). To gain a closer look at their achievement, with permission, I would like to shadow them for a day (S4) during school time. Although there is a concern that students might feel obliged to “put on a show,” based on my experience, if I sit together with students instead of sitting and observing at a distance, this method could be effective.

6.2 Constraints of assessment

Potential constraints on the assessments could arise from stakeholders’ misunderstandings and learners’ uneasiness during tests. For some Chinese parents who are anxious about grades, it will not be easy for them to receive comments instead of a grade report. Some of them might expect more formal, extensive

training and a heavier load of homework, such as copying vocabulary multiple times to produce correct spellings. For this reason, it is imperative to include them in the assessment process, for example, assisting with homework, and to clarify the validity and reliability of the ongoing assessment. For YLs, it is not uncommon (indeed it is understandable) that they could feel nervous when being observed. Possible extreme reactions of learners include observing the examiner's reaction rather than engaging with others, not being willing to contribute constructively due to their concern about making mistakes and responding passively with simple words. Therefore, it is essential to make sure students understand the assessment criteria through prior interviews to put them at ease.

7 Conclusions

In general, I consider that the course proposal has demonstrated consistency with the main principles discussed. As for the notional aspect, these elements are introduced and categorised by situations for direct use. Tasks are effectively used to support learners' understanding and to give them practice of language use, as well as being designed as a series of rehearsals for them to get a taste of what to expect in real situations. A learning-centred approach greatly elevates learners' class engagement; for example, during the work on the topic of food, the content was rich and the topic was expanded, so that they were able to talk about recipes and ways of cooking with a passion which was beyond my expectation. The immersive environment also has served as a stronger foundation for them to participate in other subject classes.

Through my observations, I noted various changes in their confidence and use of language: raising their hands to answer questions; Xavier recounting a fight that happened in a PE lesson; Olivia's friends coming to me and praising her language progress – all proved they are progressing well.

Lastly, it is undeniable that there were certain limitations, including the small size of the class and the fixed membership of the group, which marginally impaired the effectiveness of the course. There was not a great difference in proficiency among the three, and therefore, peer learning was not as common as anticipated. Occasionally, I would intervene and provide extra support to keep an activity going. Also, students should have more opportunities to present their work and performance through individual projects, which could motivate them exponentially.

Appendix A

Course Plan

Lesson	Theme	Content	Materials	Linguistic knowledge	Final Communicative Task
1-2H	Who are you? (SP1, L1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask and answer where they are from • Greetings • Give personal information including age, interests, habits, hometown, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video • Flashcards and other visual aids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where are you from? • I am... • Nice to meet you. • I like... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role-play • Ss pretend to welcome parents to school as school ambassadors

3-4H	Family and friends (SP1, SP2, L1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe people Family relationships Job 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students each brings a picture of their family Appendix 4.2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Doctor/businessman/... Parents/grandparents/sister Brother/ Adverbs of frequency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meet my family Ss introduce their family to the class
5-6H	My school life (R8, SP2, L4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School timetable Subjects I learn Learning tools in classroom 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pencil box Learning tools in the classroom (Appendix 4.1) Their own timetable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science/drama... Morning/afternoon/ Board/projector/printer/marker/ Can I borrow... questions for making requests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Draw my timetable. Ss use learning tools as hints to elicit the name of the subject from the class
7-8H	A school tour (SP3, L4, R11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Names of different rooms What can you see in this room? What can we do in here? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School layout map Cardboard, colour pens Room names 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hall/toilet/office/staff room Ask and give information Make and reply to requests and offers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Draw our school floor plan (group work) Ss take turns leaving the classroom and come back with the room names and peers help put them on the sketch
9-10H	Let's work together (SP 3, SP2, SP1, L5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construct shapes and objects with magnets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Magnets from the science teacher Pictures from art teacher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Talk about problems React to problems and give suggestions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Charade games Ss work on their own shapes and have other guess what objects they are
11-12H	Are you well? (SP3, SP1, L7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotional and physical status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Props borrowed from EYFS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Express problems Ask for help React to advices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Role-play Ss have prompts and go to see a doctor

13-14H	My life outside the school (R9, R10, R11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My leisure activity • Places I have been to in the city • Transportation tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City map • Props borrowed from EYFS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expressions for making plans • Narrate • Offer and accept invitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design a school trip (group work) • Ss discuss and design this trip and give a presentation
15-16H	Food (R9, R6, L4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sections in a supermarket • Main categories of food • How to make a pizza 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A pizza shop menu • Supermarket flyer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrate/Make statement • Express and object opinions • Give instructions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Let's make a pizza • Write down family shopping list • Role-play • Ss play waiters and customers in a restaurant
17-18H	How much is this? (SP1, R8, R11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number 1-100 • Bills/coins • Quantification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Props borrowed from EYFS • Price tags/labels • fake money 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ask and grant information • ask for permission • give compliments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role-play in a shop • Ss play customers and shopping assistant
19-20H	Animals and their habitat (R10, R9, R11, L4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animals, their appearance and geographical features 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flashcards • Documentary clip 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn to reason and explain • Make statements based on facts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Story-telling: Who let the peacock out? • T tells a story about a morning, the zookeeper discovers the peacock is gone. Each S has one card describes the animal they think has let the peacock out

Note. SP refers to spoken production, L refers to listening, and R refers to reading, 1-11 refers to the implications listed under priorities emerging from needs analysis and diagnostic testing

Appendix B

Table B1

Observation Notes for Needs Analysis

Learners can...	Barely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Reading				
1. Get the gist of a story	x			
2. Infer a new word with illustrations		x		
3. Infer a new word without illustrations	x			
4. Comprehend Instructions on worksheets		x		
5. Board work	x			
6. Notice letters on the notice board	x			
Listening				
7. Comprehend teacher's instructions		x		
8. Comprehend peer's oral responses to teacher's questions	x			
9. Comprehend audio resources	x			
10. Understand their peers' speaking in a conversation in a class		x		
11. Understand the aim and the gist of the question in general school setting	x			
12. Distinguish questions from general statements		x		
13. Can catch the key information of a short listening material	x			
Speaking				
14. Give brief answers to teacher's questions that are related to teaching		x		
15. Ask questions	x			
16. Participate in group discussions	x			
17. Greetings		x		
18. Express feelings	x			
19. Share personal information about themselves		x		
20. Share simple reflection about a story	x			
21. Recount a story	x			

Table B2

Observation Notes for Each Learner

	Learning habits	Strengths
Student 1	This student is attentive and tries hard to understand a lot of things. He also seems to desire a high level of accuracy as long as he understands what is asked of him; he is prompt in answering questions and he feels good when the teacher approves his performance	Conversations about a familiar topic, following instructions that require total physical responses, speaking out loud when he is sure about the answer
Student 2	This student can maintain a relative high level of participation in the class, yet she seems to withdraw herself from others from time to time when she struggles a lot, she prefers to work on her own for most of the time	Individual writing work, transcription
Student 3	This student has a relatively lower motivation, she does not seem very keen to try to understand everything in the class, she tries to rely on her existing knowledge to understand new language points and she feels frustrated when she fails	Inferring; make sentences by using learnt sentence structure; pair work

Appendix C

Questionnaire sample

Ranking survey

Please indicate with a X on the line scaling from 0-10 to show the degree of your favouritism.

Example: I am ready to say things about me. (S2P1)

0	10
x	

Q1: I can say more words now. (S2P1)

0	10
	x

Q2: I can guess the meaning of a sentence now. (S2P2)

0	10
	x

Q3: I can talk about school events now. (S2P3)

0	10
	x

Q4: I can follow what a teacher says in class now. (S2P4)

0	10
	x

Q5: I can talk to my friends now. (S2P5)

0	10
	x

Q6: I like reading books now. (S2P6)

0	10
	x

Q7: I can do activities now because I understand what to do. (S2P7)

0	10
	x

Q8: I can ask questions when I do not understand. (S2P8)

0	10
	x

Q9: I can ask for help from teachers and classmates now. (S2P9)

0	10
x	

Q10: I can tell a story if I read it. (S2P10)

0	10
x	

Note. The related implications in the bracket will be omitted in the students' version.

References

- Bailey, K. (1997). *Learning about language assessment: Dilemmas, decisions, and directions*. Heinle ELT.
- Blatchford, C. (1971). A theoretical contribution to ESL diagnostic test construction. *TESOL Quarterly*, 5(3), 209-215.
- Breen, M. P., & Candlin, C. N. (1980). The essentials of a communicative curriculum in language teaching. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(2), 89–112. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/i.2.89>
- Brown, J.D. (1995). Needs analysis. *The elements of language curriculum: A systematic approach to program development*. Heinle & Heinle
- Cameron, L. (2001). *Teaching languages to young learners*. Ernst Klett Sprachen.
- Candlin, C. (1987). Towards task-based language learning. *Language learning tasks*, 7, 5-22.
- Ellis, G., & Brewster, J. (2002). *The storytelling handbook for primary English language teachers*. Penguin.
- Finocchiaro, M., & Brumfit, C. J. (1983). *The functional-notional approach: From theory to practice*. Oxford University Press.
- Ferrance, E. (2000). *Action research*. Northeast Islands Regional Education Laboratory.
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second-language learning*. Newbury House.
- Gipps, C. (1994). *Beyond Testing*. The Falmer Press.
- Graves, K. (ed) (1996). *Teachers as course developers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Graves, K. (2000). *Designing language course*. Heinle & Heinle.
- Halliwell, S., & Halliwell, S. (1992). *Teaching English in the primary classroom*. Longman.
- Harley, B. (1994). Appealing to consciousness in the L2 classroom. *AILA Review*, 2, 57-68.
- Hasslegreen, A., & Caudwell, G. (2016). *British Council Monographs on Modern Language Testing*. <https://www.britishcouncil.org/exam/aptis/research/publications/monograph-series>
- Hughes, A. (1989). *Testing for languages teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Johnson, R. K., & Swain, M. (1997). *Immersion education: International perspectives*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139524667>
- Lightbown, P., & Spada, N. M. (1999). *How languages are learned*. Oxford University Press.
- Linse, C.T. (1993). Assessing student needs. In S. Hudelson (Ed.), *English as a second language curriculum resource handbook* (pp. 35-48). Krause International.
- Martinez, B. I. (2007). A story-based approach to teaching English. *Encuentro*, 17, 52-56.

- Nagy, W. E., et al. (1985). Learning words from context. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 20(2), 233–253.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/747758>
- Nunan, D. (1988). *Syllabus design*. Oxford University Press.
- Piaget, J., & Inhelder, B. (1969). *The psychology of the child*. Basic Books.
- Read, C. (2008). *500 activities for the primary classroom*. Oxford University Press.
- Richards, J. C. (2001). *Curriculum development in language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1997). *The collected works of L. S. Vygotsky Vol. 3: Problems of the theory and history of psychology*. Plenum Press.
- Weir, C. & Roberts, J. (1994). *Evaluation in ELT*. Blackwell.
- Willis, D., & Willis, J. (2007). *Doing task based teaching*. Oxford University Press.
- Yalden, J. (1987). *Principles of course design for language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.

Yanwei Sun is an ESL/EFL/EAL teacher from China, currently working in Hangzhou Yungu High School. Her teaching practice has been with students aged 7 to 20 but now mainly high school students. She is a certified DELTA teacher, as well as a teacher trainer authorized by Cambridge Assessment. Recently, she has helped National Geographic revise *The voice* textbook (upcoming series).